

The Entertainment Industry in Kenya: An Analysis of Multi-Choice Limited's Organizational Performance and Competitive Strategies

¹* Alice Mildred Okeyo

¹MML Student: Management University of Africa
P. O. Box. 29677-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

²*Brown Kitur

² Management University of Africa
P. O. Box. 29677-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

Abstract:- The main objective was to determine the competitive strategies and organizational performance of the entertainment industry in Kenya through a case study of Multi-choice Limited. Specific objectives included examining the effect of cost leadership strategy and differentiation strategy on the performance of the organization at Multi-choice Limited. The Resource-Based View and Contingency Theory support the Competitive Advantage Theory, which serves as the study's primary anchor theory. The study, population was 185, and a sample size of 92 was selected using stratified random selection. Questionnaires were used during the data collection process. To take part in the pilot study, ten Star-Times Kenya Limited employees were chosen at random. SPSS and fundamental statistics were used to examine the quantitative data. The data was presented using tables and graphics. According to the study, cost leadership strategy, and differentiation strategy influence the organization's performance. According to the recommendation given, Multi-choice Limited should choose to follow a cost-leadership strategy and differentiation strategy and concentrate more on gaining a competitive edge by having the lowest expenses in the industry. Multi-choice Limited's management should think about incorporating cost leadership principles within the organization's divisions and departments. The study suggests further research on the effects of organizational structure, forms of ownership, and strategic alliances on competitive strategies in Kenya's entertainment sector. Further research should be carried out to validate its findings.

Keywords:- *Cost-Leadership Strategy, Differentiation Strategy, Competitive Strategies, Organizational Performance, Entertainment Industry, Multi-choice Limited.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Universally, several economic sectors have experienced fierce rivalry between businesses as a result of shifting business conditions. Because of the rivalry, businesses have had to create methods to maintain their operations and maintain market competitiveness. To compete and raise their profitability and market share, they must perform better, businesses have sought this transformation in operations through the adoption of general strategies. There is a requirement for an organization to advance beyond resolving current issues and enhance the

shifting situations it encounters brought up by the ongoing changing business environment. However, because of its complexity, the environment presents problems that cannot be easily handled. To adapt to changing demands, this has compelled firms to create and implement strategic methods (Bragg, 2015). A reflective assessment of the environment is required, according to Thomas, Hunger, Hoffman, and Bamford (2020), since firms' profitability, market share, and level of global competitiveness are all in peril. This is an unavoidable truth that strengthens proactive action, aids in strategy building, and raises market share competition.

The relationship between performance and competitive strategies in various industries and organizations from a global viewpoint has been the subject of several studies in the US. In their study, Greene and Yao (2016) looked at market strategy and nonmarket issues in the markets for radio and television audience measurement. Results demonstrated that two characteristics politically bounded regional markets and markets with inherent monopolistic properties significantly characterize both market strategies and the nonmarket constraints that restrict such strategies. Even if the pre-monopoly period or times of competition may only last a short while, they are nonetheless important. Monopolists engage in a nonmarket strategy to avoid unfavourable limitations and reputational harm, as well as market strategies to guarantee that they are not superseded. Depending on their legal and regulatory circumstances, customers of the measurement services have used both market and nonmarket methods to minimize the market strength of the audience measurement corporations (Greene & Yao, 2016).

The two state-owned broadcasters in New Zealand were the subject of a study by Grey (2018) that examined both active and passive global marketing techniques. The study's findings revealed that Significant differences existed between the two national state-owned broadcasters' levels of internationalization and financial success. Little profit was made from its overseas assets, which caused Television New Zealand, the more aggressive international marketer, to continue growing and expanding its global business while Radio New Zealand, which had taken a more passive, reactive strategy, to de-internationalize. Management traits, notably degrees of expertise, orientation, and dedication in international companies, strongly influence how Internationalization is thought of as an experienced process for choosing where to spend in worldwide marketing. It also

shows that environmental factors have a big impact on managers' goals and expectations, the rules and methods they use, and the levels of internationalization and success of their businesses (Gray, 2018).

Omanje (2018) looked at how internet television (TV) is believed to affect pay TV company performance in Kenya as an emerging technology. The results showed that the high cost of internet connection and slow rollout of reliable fibre are the biggest barriers to internet TV adoption. The poll found that using unreliable Wi-Fi was the most common way of accessing the internet. The simplest way to receive a signal for Kenyan pay TV is via cable or telluric indicator transmission, both of which these businesses have made significant investments in. The poll also revealed that people watch TV for only a short amount of time, which means pay-TV providers need to improve the way they distribute content. The primary market stakeholders were determined by a comprehensive content repository, a competitive pricing plan, and an appealing user interface. Exclusive and intriguing programming would boost growth and prevent customer turnover, and inferences exposed; Kenyans have access to several pay-TV services from various providers (Omanje, 2018). Businesses that lack a unique selling proposition and Copying others cause them to lose their competitive advantage, which increases the likelihood that they will do worse than their competitors (Das & Canel, 2023). In Kenya Atikiya and Nzulwa (2014) claim that organizational elements including strategic planning, technological know-how, and product quality are thought to significantly affect an organization's outstanding performance. In this context, several competitive strategies for the organization have been created and rigorously evaluated. Particularly, Porter's generic strategy, which is frequently linked to better performance and also serves as the foundation of the present study, is considered the skeleton for strategic management frameworks. Due to the small market and competitive environment, many firms still struggle to attain or maintain. The ability of an institution to employ resources from its business model to create money is measured subjectively by organizational performance, which is also a broad indicator of total financial capacity over time. Additionally, it may be used to contrast similar businesses operating in the same industry (Al-Tamini, 2014).

II. ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Is identified by Borman and Schmit (2016) as a multidimensional paradigm whose analysis takes a variety of elements into account. Performance may be measured using a variety of measures, and the measuring unit as a whole should be taken into consideration. The institution's liquidity, solvency, profitability, operating income, total unit sales, operational revenue, ability to repay debt, and financial efficiency are all assessed. Both internal and external factors influence performance. Competition, technology, and the workplace are among the external forces that affect performance; internal forces include aptitude, levels of motivation, competencies, and knowledge (Saeed, Jiao, Zahid, Tabassum, & Nauman, 2020). According to Sufian and Chong (2016), different metrics may be used to

assess organizational performance, and when aggregating such metrics, it is important to consider the unit of measurement. Measured criteria include operations revenue, and operational income, among others. Therefore, it is crucial to comprehend that both internal and external variables impact organizational performance across all pay TV organizations.

Performance was divided into three categories business performance, financial performance, and organizational success (Hasani & O'Reilly, 2020). Findings based on market share, innovation, and new product development are the main topics of financial performance. A more comprehensive conceptualization that takes into account the accomplishment of goals and perceived overall performance is reflected in the performance measurement of overall organization effectiveness (Liu, Ma, & Huang, 2015). When compared to the intended objectives or goals of an organization, organizational performance in the Multi-choice Limited refers to the actual outcome. One way to increase people's commitment to accomplishing stated goals is through the performance of the organization, and this study is one example. Many studies have adopted a multidimensional strategy to evaluate the performance of measures that aren't financial, as proposed by Jama (2017). Organizational development, operational effectiveness, governance, increased effectiveness in achieving strategic goals, increased staff commitment, a shared vision, fit between internal and external capabilities, and consideration of the decision's long-term effects are some of the non-financial performance measures listed above. Organizational performance is a study-dependent variable that is determined by market share, revenue collected, and new subscriptions.

III. COMPETITIVE STRATEGY

The a need for a corporation to implement competitive strategies to keep up with the evolving business climate and outperform its close competitors. Porter is credited with initially advancing the concept that a corporation must have a strategy that enables it to beat average-performing competitors. superior results in a cutthroat industry, according to Porter (1985), may be attained by pursuing a competitive strategy that includes a cost-cutting strategy, a differentiation strategy, and a focus strategy. According to Porter (1985), strategies are an essential component of every successful business strategy that a company may utilize to exploit a competitive market position. Organizational competitive strategy includes all the measures a company has done, is currently taking, keep existing clients and draw in new ones as well as withstand competitive pressure that strengthens the firm market position, serves as the cornerstone for accelerating organization performance and market share growth (Thomas, Hunger, Hoffman, & Bamford, 2020).

In a company climate that is full of turbulence and unpredictability, competitive organization strategy does provide better and enhanced organizational performance, according to Shinkle, Kriauciunas, and Hundley (2018). According to Michael Porter's study results, a combination

of three business strategies results in a condition described as being "stuck in the middle," characterized by a lack of a distinct strategy and subpar organizational performance. Contrary to this school of thought, Shinkle, et al, (2018) say that these strategies enhance and complement the grade of the company's goods and services. In this sense, rising market demand is most often the outcome of higher-quality products and services. Increased market demand, greater top market shares, and increased production all boost an organization's capacity to implement a low-cost strategy. Hansen, Nybakk, and Panwar (2015) business can employ a cost leadership strategy is one of the three competitive strategies that reduce costs along the whole value chain to attain the lowest cost structure feasible, with goods built of high-quality materials but with few conventional features, to expand market share and competitive advantage; a focus strategy in which a firm targets particular market segments by distinguishing consumer demands to provide for them at the best pricing on the market, The use of organization innovation as part of a differentiation strategy takes into account the organization's sales, marketing strategies, and advertising strategy, while also focusing on the manufacturing of products, firm performance, and quality.

IV. COST LEADERSHIP STRATEG

It enables a firm to adopt lower production costs, which helps the business generate greater profits than competitors owing to economies of scale and low production costs (Candido & Santos, 2019). An organization's use of the experience curve as a cost leadership strategy results from production and environmental investments, as well as from cost monitoring to enhance organizational performance. Summer (2018) asserts that cost leadership aims to reduce and even get rid of expenditures in several domains, such as marketing and development. Hansen, et al. (2015) emphasize and adhere to a few ideas, including economies of scale, cost-saving strategy via the learning curve, stringent cost management, and overhead expenses. A company that uses the cost leadership strategy in this case accomplishes so by adopting a low-cost strategy in comparison to its rivals. To achieve total TQM, cost leadership, large-scale facilities, process improvements, benchmarking, cost reduction, and indirect expenditure control, businesses utilize various resource allocation strategies (Banker, Mashruwala, & Tripathy, 2018).

It permits the business to charge more money than companies that use the differentiation strategy, which involves investing in new goods or services to gain a competitive edge. The cost leadership strategy builds a low-cost firm in its market niche with the primary purpose of getting an advantage over competitors by cutting operating costs below those of other market players. The concept of cost leadership revolves around organizational effectiveness. Businesses employing this technique must keep a high level of competition to sustain their profit margin over time (Bahadori, Teymourzadeh, Tajik, Mehdi, & Hosseini, 2018). As a result, they must prioritize operational efficiency across all key functional areas. The business gains operational efficiency, effective pricing leadership, industry growth,

reduced prices, greater quality, or both by implementing the strategy (Thomson, William, Gamble, & Strickland, 2020). This study, and is determined by competitive pricing, technology-based systems, administrative costs, and cost reduction.

V. DIFFERENTIATION STRATEGY

This is a tactic the company uses to boost the value of its goods and services in comparison to those of its competitors to win over customers with its unique advantages. Although consumer understanding will always determine if there is product distinction, a corporation may change these impressions in several ways. This suggests that differentiation may be done especially for a product to make it appealing or for a service by utilizing post-sales services such as quality concern, reward schemes, and longer hours. (Candido & Santos, 2019). Businesses that use distinction as a strategy prioritize dominating the market. Being the first to market allows a business to set prices whatever they choose and to get into a broader market segment to increase profit and growth margins. A firm's differentiation strategy must guarantee high product quality and prioritize innovation inside the organization for it to be performance delivering unique features, delivering excellent service, running active promotions, and creating a reputable brand (Li & Zhou, 2018). For this study differentiation strategy is the second independent variable and it is determined by value-based service, core competencies, product features and product process.

VI. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Choosing which strategy configurations to implement to perform better in the marketplaces in which they compete is a problem for corporations. This is taken into account given that global firms work in contexts that change quickly and in ways that are unpredictable. Multi-choice Limited faces competition from new entrants Zuku, Azam, mobile applications, and other rivals while dominating the pay-TV industry. The uptake of pay TV has been slow in Kenya, despite the number of service providers in the market. The going has not been easy pay-TVe pay-TV providers, to the extent that they have had to withdraw from the market. Good examples are GTV and Smart TV, which launched their programs only to leave after some time. The limited uptake of pay TV services has been attributed by the service providers to the import tax on decoders, as the taxes paid on decoders account for 45% of the cost of the gadget (CCK, 2020). The import taxes are a major discouraging factor in the uptake of pay television.

The prevailing environment in the pay-TV sector necessitates organizations such as Multi-choice to employ different strategies to cope with competition and sustain their performance. The strategies that pay TV firms employ in the face of dwindling fortunes to remain competitive and how such strategies influence organizational performance are central. In particular, intended to assess competitive strategies for Multi-choice performance (Omanje, 2018). A competitive strategy helps organizations such as Multi-choice Limited to gain a competitive advantage over the

competition. Studies in previous research are far from conclusive, findings from O'Regan, Kluth, and Parnell (2019) established there is no agreement as to what works best for organizational performance and sustained competitive advantage as most of the studies have been at the centre of strategic management. The link between competitive advantage and performance, according to Pearce and Robinson (2018), has been a contentious and unsolved issue in the field of strategic management.

Kenyan perspective, it is highlighted that studies on competitive strategy have less or no focus on the Pay TV market and more on other contexts; other studies such as Greene and Yao (2016) looked at market strategy and nonmarket issues in the markets for radio and television audience measurement and finding showed monopolists engage in a nonmarket strategy to avoid unfavorable limitations and reputational harm, as well as market strategies to guarantee that they are not superseded, the study provides a contextual gap; The two state-owned broadcasters in New Zealand were the subject of a study by Gray (2018) that looked at active and passive international marketing strategies. The study's findings revealed that the two state-owned broadcasters in the nation had achieved significantly different levels of internationalization that improved their financial performance and Omanje (2018) looked at how internet TV is believed to affect pay TV company performance in Kenya as an emerging technology. The findings revealed that TV companies need to enhance their content delivery, the studies have provided an empirical gap. As a result, this research attempted to close a knowledge gap by using Multi-choice. Hence this study sought to answer the research question: Does competitive strategies determine organizational performance in the entertainment industry in Kenya?

VII. OBJECTIVES

- To examine the effect of cost leadership strategy on the performance of the organization at Multi-choice Limited
- To determine the effect of differentiation strategy on the performance of the organization at Multi-choice Limited.

VIII. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

A. *Competitive Advantage Theory*

Porter developed this theory in 1985, and it is based on characteristics that enable businesses to beat their competitors' capital performance, expertise, and marketplace. According to the thesis, businesses should seek strategies that result in high-quality products that are priced premium. The idea places a strong emphasis on organizational productivity when discussing development and expansion as the firm's primary strategy. According to the competitive advantage argument, inexpensive labor is widely accessible and no economy needs vast natural resources to function effectively. The concept accentuates the significance of maximizing economies of scale in high-priced goods and services (Porter, 1985). The financial measurement method and establishing a position of competitive advantage will lead to increased productivity

profitability and market share (Frawley & Fahy, 2006). According to the concept, enterprises should concentrate their management strategy on achieving and maintaining a competitive advantage over their rivals since performance and competitive advantage are seen as two distinct dimensions.

The competitive advantage hypothesis, which supports the idea that effective resource management may help organizations gain a competitive advantage position and improve performance, forms the foundation of the research. It is predicated on the notion that social norms and cultural values have an impact on an organization's ability to recognize, comprehend, and translate signals from the external business environment into internal organizational and behavioural change that aids in the survival, expansion, and development of the firm. Superior company performance and efficient resource management through cost reduction (cost leadership), product comprehension (focus), and product superiority/innovation (differentiation) are achieved by three study aims.

However, the competitive advantage argument has come under fire for several of its flaws. The application of the competitive advantage theory to company performance has drawn criticism from academics. Three findings were established by Ma (2010) on the distinct trends between the competitive advantage hypothesis and corporate performance. According to Rose et al. (2010), having a competitive advantage depends on the context, competitive advantage is a relative phrase, and greater performance is not necessarily associated with having one, according to the first study. According to Rose, et al (2010) and Ma (2010), there is a probability that competitive advantage won't lead to improved firm performance since it depends on context. Therefore, improving performance is achievable without obtaining a reasonable benefit (Rose, et al, 2010).

Scholarly critiques of theory remain significant since they bring up a variety of points that must be taken into consideration. And no assurance that having a competitive edge will always translate into higher performance, and the opposite is also true. It also brings up the point that higher performance is not necessarily the result of having a competitive advantage. These objections of Rose, et al (2010) analysis are legitimate and show where the theory is flawed. The implementation of the theory has to be improved due to the limitations of the theory, as noted by academics. How It adapts to shifts in the commercial environment by which it operates will determine how well it performs, although core resources are simpler to manage, for the competitive advantage theory to be effective. Using the competitive advantage theory, plans must take shifting business settings to attain superior performance.

The competitive advantage argument has flaws because it assumes that competitive advantage will always translate into greater performance regardless of external circumstances. In addition to the theory, the study also takes into account the contingency theory, as will be discussed below. Contingency theory encourages ways to attain greater performance by utilizing both effective management

of internal resources and responding to contingencies in the external environment. The theory was adopted for this study because it supports the variable of differentiation, cost leadership and performance.

B. Resource-Based View

In 1959, Penrose established this theory, but Wernerfelt's work in 1984 helped make it more widely known for its applicability in analyzing organizational performance (Kozlenkova, et al, 2014). Wernerfelt claimed that the internal resources of the company are the true drivers of its performance and profitability. The phrase "RBV" generally refers to the viewpoint that believes in resources. This early understanding of the resource-based view is attributed to Penrose's research from that year (Kozlenkova, Samaha, & Palmatier, 2014). These resources are arranged so that they are thought of as internal resources that the company already has. The RBV viewpoint's advantages were furthered by Jay Barney, whose work has since gained traction. He outlined the key internal resource characteristics and their connection to competitive advantages, a company has a competitive advantage when it can generate more economic value than its nearest competition in a certain market (Kozlenkova, Samaha, & Palmatier, 2014).

Later works by him distinguished a temporary competitive advantage from a long-term competitive advantage. According to Gills, Combs, and Ketchen (2014), not all organizational resources are necessary for it to create a competitive advantage. An organization's resources must be challenging to duplicate, replace, or transfer for them to reach the position where they can generate profits. According to Gills, Combs, and Ketchen (2014), The ability to employ company resources, which are inventories of immediately usable components possessed by the firm, differs from the corporation's competencies. The features and forms of resources that generate an edge, higher performance, and competitive advantage are all components of the RBV theory (Gillis, et al, 2014).

Kozlenkova, (2014), RBV refers to the use of a variety of a firm's accessible tangible and intangible resources. These resources must be diverse for any company to convert its organizational strategy into a lasting economic gain. The RBV clarifies how a business can outperform its competitors. The RBV theory places a focus on the organization's internal resources when implementing its strategy. RBV theory proponents like Jensen, et al (2016) contend that for businesses to perform better, it is preferable to repurpose current resources as opposed to trying to acquire new resources or skills for every opportunity. There are two categories of these resources. According to the theory, a company must identify its special resources and decide where to use them to maximize profits. RBV also contends that cost leadership strategies are important performance indicators that enhance a company's competitiveness and performance and can establish and preserve an economic gain (Hitt, et al, 2016).

Although core resources are significant drivers of organizational performance, the RBV theory is constrained by its exclusive emphasis on the internal environment as a means of maximizing a company's superior performance (Gillis, Combs, & Ketchen, 2014). The RBV has an external environment that affects the firm's performance and competitive advantage. The truth is that outside factors have an equal impact on how a firm performs in the market. External variables, such as rules and regulations, taxation, sectoral policies, and compliance procedures, have an impact on how enterprises function in the market. When examining elements that can influence the strategies it can use, external resources must also be taken into account. To study strategies that produce superior performance, it is vital to consider both external factors and a firm's internal resources, as suggested by theory (Hitt, et al, 2016). Despite its flaws, the theory is chosen as a supplementary concept. The RBV is still a crucial principle for describing how a firm can use the instruments available to it for enhancing performance, and for this study, the variables that are supported by this theory include cost leadership and differentiation strategy.

C. Configuration Theory

The school of thinking that Chandler founded in 1962, which was later elaborated upon by Mintzberg and Miller in 1970, Miles and Snow in 1987, and Mintzberg and Miller in the 1960s and early 1970s, served as the foundation for the theory's development. According to configuration theory, performance is influenced by how well its design fits with its surroundings. The theory's fundamental premise is that an organization performs at its peak when its structure corresponds to an external contingency element. And only businesses that match their operations to the current environment do their best work. According to the notion, a company's strategy, structure, and external environment must all fit together well for it to be effective (Fincham & Rhodes, 2010). According to Geo, Zhou, and Yim (2007), any organization's external environment is exogenous. Research on the theory has repeatedly shown that fit among features of the organization is a key predictor of performance. There are no universally ideal strategic options for all organizations, thus the company must modify its strategy to the environmental restrictions (Gao, Zhou, & Yim, 2007).

Other academics have criticized this theory to a certain extent, claiming that it cannot adequately reflect organizational dynamics or alter the complexity of its adherents, as Smith and Lewis (2011) have done. The theory has also been critiqued by Ployhart and Vandenberg (2010), who argue that it must take time and change into account when creating models that account for the natural impact of change through time on the causal link between two conceptions. The theory highlights how Based on the choice of a competitive strategy based on background changes as well as the demand, competitive strategies and competitive intensity of the external environment influence organizational performance of having a fit and how competitive strategy affects how well a business performs. Because it supports and works with all four research

variables cost leadership, and differentiation strategy, it is employed in the study.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

IX. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive research approach. The objective of the descriptive study approach was to describe behaviour without in any way modifying it. Before applying quantitative research designs, the design is typically used to find useful cues about the variables that were examined (Bordens & Abbott, 2017). The research study employed a quantitative research design since the main objective is frequently to better understand the research study, thus the findings should be able to be used across a wide range of institutions. The study focused on 185 Multi-choice Limited. employees, including non-management personnel and managers at the senior, medium, and entry levels. The study used stratified random sampling, which Creswell and Creswell (2018) found to be objective and give all populations an equal chance of being chosen. stratified random sampling was used, which Creswell and Creswell (2018) found to be objective and give the entire population an equal chance of being chosen. Kothari and Garg (2015), a sample is the division used in representing a large unit to reflect the features of the population. Cooper and Schindler (2018) noted that to prevent biases, the study sample size should be random and 1-10% of the target population is regarded as a suitable size, according to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill's (2018) recommendation. Due to the limited number of employees, this study adopted a 50% representation, 92 participants were the sample.

Questionnaires are preferred by the researcher since the study that has used them and questionnaires are recommended to be economical and they are easily administered as well as time-saving (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2018). The questionnaire in the study is preferred based on other researchers who have used them in the same subject area. Questionnaires are considered to be cheaper instruments of data collection and the researcher can obtain volumes, however, noted that the questionnaire's only disadvantage is cannot be administered to illiterate respondents not able to read and write (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The researcher used questionnaires because it makes it possible and easy for correlation, descriptive, and inferential statistical analysis as echoed by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2018). These questions also will aid in enriching the qualitative methodology effectively. The questionnaire further provides anonymity as most respondents don't prefer their identity revealed. Primary data

D. Conceptual framework

The study was guided by a conceptual framework that presents and defines the viewpoints that attempt to explain the research problem under the study.

was collected using questionnaires while secondary data used in the literature review is collected from documented sources such as journals, monographs, articles, books, and company reports.

The qualitative data were analyzed using simple statistics and SPSS. The raw data gathered from the field was coded before the generalization of the findings was made. The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presentations were in tables. Inferential statistics were used to show the connection that exists between the study variables. The study used the Pearson correlation matrix was used. Pearson correlation helped in predicting and describing the association between the variables in terms of magnitude and direction. The correlation test at a 5% level of significance with a 2-tailed test was conducted. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was adopted to disclose the complete model significance. The calculated f statistic was compared with the tabulated f statistic. A critical p-value of 0.05 was used to determine whether the overall model was significant or not.

X. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data was analyzed using 77 valid questionnaires. Out of the 77 responses that were used for analysis, the majority of responders, based on the responses (57%) were more male than female (43%), Male responders, on the other hand, were more than their female counterparts. Kothari and Garg (2015), one of the most crucial variables in understanding respondents' attitudes toward themes is their gender. the age range of 30% of respondents was between 36 and 40. 25% of participants were aged 31 to 35. 17% of the population was between the ages of 40 and 45, while 13% was in the 26–30 age range. 5% of the population was between the ages of 18 and 25 and 10% were above the age of 46. The responses show a good distribution throughout the age range, and the bulk of staff are young and energetic. Most of the participants held a bachelor's degree, closely followed by those who had master's degrees, college degrees, and doctorates, respectively. This demonstrates that professional input is necessary for work at the organization. The majority of respondents said they had been employed by the organization for between six and ten years, followed by the ones who had worked between one and five years, then eleven and fifteen years, and more than sixteen years were the least. The majority had worked for Multi-choice

Limited for more than five years and, therefore, were able to comprehend its dynamics. Kothari and Garg (2015) claim that respondents with extensive experience in an

organization are better able to comprehend its dynamics and provide authoritative answers to research questions.

Table 1: Correlation Matrix

Variables		Organization Performance	Cost Leadership Strategy	Differentiation Strategy
Organization Performance	Pearson Correlation	1.000		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
Cost Leadership Strategy	Pearson Correlation	.765**	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		
Differentiation Strategy	Pearson Correlation	.522**	.314**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	

Table 1 demonstrates how Multi-choice Limited's cost leadership strategy was connected to and significantly correlated with organizational success ($r = 0.765$, $p = 0.000$). This implied that an improvement would lead to better performance in Multi-choice Limited since the cost leadership strategy had a good and substantial influence.

Differentiation Strategy has a favourable relationship with performance at Multi-choice Limited and substantial way as shown by ($r = 0.522$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This also suggested that because the Differentiation Strategy had a favourable and significant impact, improving it will result in better performance in Multi-choice Limited.

Table 2: Model Summary for Cost Leadership

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.642 ^a	.499	.395	.60906

a. Predictors: (Constant), Cost Leadership

The link between the dependent variable, organizational performance, and the predictor component, cost leadership strategy, is shown in Table 2. $R = 0.642$ suggests a strong positive relationship between the cost leadership strategy and organizational success, and $R^2 =$

0.499 suggests that a change in the cost leadership strategy might account for 49.9% of the variation in organizational performance. Organizational performance at Multi-choice Limited is influenced at 50.1% by other factors.

Table 3: ANOVA^a Results for Cost Leadership

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	26.578	1	26.578	75.042	.000 ^b
1 Residual	42.902	76	.375		
Total	69.480	77			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Cost Leadership Strategy

$F = 75.042$ values in Table 3 show that the cost leadership strategy has a significant influence on performance, proving that the model fits the data well and that cost leadership strategy has a significant impact on

Multi-choice Limited performance. When 000, which is less than 0.05, is used as the significance threshold, the regression model successfully predicts the dependent variable.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients^a for Cost Leadership Strategy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.095	.431		3.309	.001	.439	1.751
Cost Leadership Strategy	.688	.079	.632	8.668	.000	.531	.845

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

Table 4 demonstrates how Multi-choice Limited's cost leadership strategy has a significant positive influence on organizational performance. The statistics show that the cost leadership strategy and performance have a substantial relationship; $p = 0.01$ (0.05). Since the value of this strategy is statistically significant ($t = 8.668$, $p.05$), increasing the mean index of the cost leadership method should improve

organizational performance by 688 units or 68.8%. The regression model that explains the results in Table 4 is as follows. Cost Leadership Strategy = $1.095 + 0.688$ for organizational performance. The model illustrates and explains how Multi-choice Limited's performance is impacted by the cost leadership strategy.

Table 5: Model Summary for Differentiation Strategy

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.595 ^a	.431	.325	.6427

a. Predictors: (Constant), Differentiation Strategy

In a regression study, the differentiation strategy, predictor component, and dependent variable were all organizational performance. The results of the regression study indicate that differentiation strategy and organizational performance have a fundamental relationship

(R = 0.595), and this relationship has an R² value of 0.431, which indicates that a change in differentiation strategy of one unit may account for 43.1% of the variance in organizational performance. The findings are summarized in Table 5.

Table 6: ANOVA^a Results for Differentiation Strategy

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	24.411	1	24.411	56.864	.000 ^b
1 Residual	46.628	76	.484		
Total	70.039	77			

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Differentiation Strategy

F = 56.864 demonstrates that differentiation strategy considerably affects organizational performance, proving that the model adequately accounts for the data and that Multi-choice Limited's performance is significantly

influenced by its differentiation strategy. Table 6 illustrates that the regression model accurately predicts the dependent variable at a significance level of .000, or less than 0.05.

Table 7: Regression Coefficients^a for Differentiation Strategy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.739	.545		2.873	.000	.669	1.069
Differentiation Strategy	.644	.186	.476	8.412	.000	.547	.823

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

According to the study's findings, Multi-choice Limited has greatly improved organizational performance by using a differentiation strategy. The findings demonstrate a strong relationship between differentiation strategy and organizational performance; p 0.05 (P = 0.01). In light of this, the values of the differentiation technique are statistically significant (t = 7.480) meaning that increasing

the mean index of differentiation strategy by .644 points should improve performance. Organizational Performance = 1.739 + 0.644 (Differentiation Strategy) is the regression equation that explains the data in Table 7. The model shows that the differentiation strategy has a favourable effect on organizational performance at Multi-choice Limited.

Table 8: Model Summary Multivariate Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.648 ^a	.568	.452	.58289

a. Predictors: (Constant) differentiation strategy, cost leadership strategy

The regression model was applied to forecast the effectiveness of the organization and competitive strategies. The results demonstrate a positive connection of

R = 0.648 and R² = .568, which means that a change in all of the predictor factors, as shown in Table 8, may explain 56.8% of the variation in the organisation.

Table 9: ANOVA^a Results for Model Summary

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	32.678	4	8.169	24.210	.000 ^b
1 Residual	37.118	73	.337		
Total	69.796	77			

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant) differentiation strategies, cost leadership strategies

The findings of F = 24.210 demonstrate that the model well describes the data and that competing strategies have a considerable impact on Multi-choice Limited's performance. These figures show that every predictor variable has a

statistically significant impact on organizational success. The dependent variable is substantially predicted by the whole regression model at the level of significance of 0.000, or less than 0.05, according to Table 9.

Table 10: Regression Coefficientsa for Multivariate Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.564	.367		1.504	.136	.176	1.281
Cost Leadership	.368	.118	.329	3.027	.003	.123	.592
Differentiation	.317	.114	.274	2.697	.008	.081	.532

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

The study's findings show that predictor factors significantly improve the organizational performance of Multi-choice Limited. (p = 0.05; P = 0.01) The numbers show a direct link between effective competition strategies and organizational performance. Consequently, at p.05, the predictor variable values are statistically significant, meaning that increasing organizational performance should be the mean index of predictive dynamics. Table 10 provides a summary of the findings. The model revealed that cost leadership strategy and differentiation strategy have effects on the organization's performance. As a result, the regression model for the study is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2$$

Where:

Y= Organizational performance

(Bi; i=1, 2, 3,4) = various coefficients for the independent variables

Xi for;

X1= Cost Leadership

X2= Differentiation

Organizational Performance = .564 + .368 (Cost Leadership) + .317 (Differentiation)

XI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Multi-choice Limited's performance is significantly impacted favourably by the predictor factors. According to the findings, competitive strategy and organizational performance are significantly correlated. Therefore, a rise in the predictor variables' mean index should enhance organizational performance, given their values are statistically significant with p.05. The regression analysis demonstrates a substantial positive link between cost leadership strategy and organizational performance, and variations in organizational performance may be attributed to changes in cost leadership strategy. The study's findings demonstrate that the regression model correctly accounts for the data and that cost leadership strategy has a substantial impact on Multi-choice Limited's performance. The regression analysis shows a significant positive link between differentiation strategy and organizational performance, and differences in organizational performance may be attributed to changes in differentiation strategy. The study's findings demonstrate that the differentiation strategy of Multi-choice Limited statistically and significantly affects organisational performance, demonstrating that the regression model correctly accounts for the data and that the differentiation strategy has a big impact on the performance of the company.

The research study offers the management and board of directors of Multi-Choice Limited the following recommendations for enhancement: Multi-choice Limited's management should opt to follow It should focus more on establishing a competitive edge by having the lowest overheads in the industry as opposed to pursuing a cost leadership strategy. Multi-choice Limited's management should think about incorporating cost leadership principles within the organization's divisions and departments. According to the study, staff members, especially managers and supervisors, should sometimes participate in training sessions and workshops to get the knowledge and skills necessary to stay up with the dynamics of constantly changing environmental circumstances. Because product differentiation has the strongest correlation with organizational effectiveness, the study suggests adopting it. In this respect, Multi-choice Limited Management ought to make an effort to offer its goods either at a price that is average in the industry at a price that is below average to win over customers or at a bigger profit margin than its competitors. Multi-choice Limited's management should consider employing market-focus strategies that are concentrated on a limited segment and seek to either acquire a cost advantage or differentiate within that sector. The study recommends more studies on the effects of organizational structure, forms of ownership, and strategic alliances on competitive strategies in Kenya's entertainment sector. This additional research should aim to shed more light and validate its findings.

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